

Supplemental Material

Thermal transport through single molecule junctions

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Computational Methods

Geometry optimization: The geometry of each structure in the paper was relaxed to the force tolerance of 10 meV/Å using the SIESTA¹ implementation of density functional theory (DFT), with a double- ζ polarized basis set (DZP) and the Generalized Gradient Approximation (GGA) functional with Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) parameterization. A real-space grid was defined with an equivalent energy cut-off of 250 Ry.

Phonon transport: Following the method described in^{2,3} a set of xyz coordinates were generated by displacing each atom from the relaxed xyz geometry in the positive and negative x , y and z directions with $\delta q' = 0.01\text{Å}$. The forces $F_i^q = (F_i^x, F_i^y, F_i^z)$ in three directions $q_i = (x_i, y_i, z_i)$ on each atom were then calculated and used to construct the dynamical matrix $D_{ij} = K_{ij}^{qq'}/M_{ij}$ where the mass matrix $M = \sqrt{M_i M_j}$ and $K_{ij}^{qq'} = [F_i^q(\delta q'_j) - F_j^q(-\delta q'_i)]/2\delta q'_j$ for $i \neq j$ obtained from finite differences. To satisfy momentum conservation, the K for $i = j$ (diagonal terms) is calculated from $K_{ii} = -\sum_{i \neq j} K_{ij}$. The phonon transmission $T_{ph}(\omega)$ then can be calculated from the relation $T_{ph}(\omega) = \text{Trace}(\Gamma_L^{ph}(\omega)G_{ph}^R(\omega)\Gamma_R^{ph}(\omega)G_{ph}^{R\dagger}(\omega))$ where $\Gamma_{L,R}^{ph}(\omega) = i(\sum_{L,R}^{ph}(\omega) - \sum_{L,R}^{ph\dagger}(\omega))$ describes the level broadening due to the coupling to the left L and right R electrodes, $\sum_{L,R}^{ph}(\omega)$ are the retarded self-frequencies associated with this coupling and $G_{ph}^R = (\omega^2 I - D - \sum_L^{ph} - \sum_R^{ph})^{-1}$ is the retarded Green's function, where D and I are the dynamical and the unit matrices, respectively. When an incident phonon of frequency ω resonates with a normal mode ψ of frequency Ω , the width of the resonance is proportional to the imaginary part of the self energy, $\Gamma = \Gamma_a + \Gamma_b$. If ψ_a and ψ_b are amplitudes of vibration of the normal mode on the atoms a and b of the molecule that connect to the electrodes, then Γ_a is proportional to ψ_a^2 and Γ_b is proportional to ψ_b^2 . ψ_a^2 is proportional to the local density of vibrational states at atom a and ψ_b^2 is proportional to the local density of states at atom b . The phonon thermal conductance κ_{ph} at temperature T is then calculated from $\kappa_{ph}(T) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \hbar\omega T_{ph}(\omega) \frac{\partial f_{BE}(\omega, T)}{\partial T} d\omega$ where $f_{BE}(\omega, T) = (e^{\hbar\omega/k_B T} - 1)^{-1}$ is Bose-Einstein

distribution function and \hbar is reduced Planck's constant and $k_B = 8.6 \times 10^{-5} eV/K$ is Boltzmann's constant.

Electron transport: To calculate the electronic properties of the device, from the converged DFT calculation, the underlying mean-field Hamiltonian H was combined with our quantum transport code, *Gollum*⁴. This yields the transmission coefficient $T_{el}(E)$ for electrons of energy E (passing from the source to the drain) via the relation

$T_{el}(E) = Tr(\Gamma_L^{el}(E)G_{el}^R(E)\Gamma_R^{el}(E)G_{el}^{R\dagger}(E))$ where $\Gamma_{L,R}^{el}(E) = i(\Sigma_{L,R}^{el}(E) - \Sigma_{L,R}^{el\dagger}(E))$ describes the level broadening due to the coupling between left L and right R electrodes and the central scattering region, $\Sigma_{L,R}^{el}(E)$ are the retarded self-energies associated with this coupling and $G_{el}^R = (ES - H - \Sigma_L^{el} - \Sigma_R^{el})^{-1}$ is the retarded Green's function, where H is the Hamiltonian and S is the overlap matrix obtained from *SIESTA* implementation of DFT. Since the DFT Fermi energy is inaccurate, we have carried out spectral adjustment using DFT+ Σ method as described by Sadeghi et al.³. Table S1 shows the total corrections to Kohn-Sham DFT energy levels.

Thermoelectric properties: Using the approach explained by Sadeghi et al.³, the electrical conductance $G_{el}(T) = G_0 L_0$ and the electronic contribution of the thermal conductance $\kappa_{el}(T) = (L_0 L_2 - L_1^2)/hTL_0$ are calculated from the electron transmission coefficient $T_{el}(E)$ where the momentums $L_n(T) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dE (E - E_F)^n T_{el}(E) \left(-\frac{\partial f_{FD}(E,T)}{\partial E}\right)$ and $f_{FD}(E, T)$ is the Fermi-Dirac probability distribution function $f_{FD}(E, T) = (e^{(E-E_F)/k_B T} + 1)^{-1}$, T is the temperature, E_F is the Fermi energy, $G_0 = 2e^2/h$ is the conductance quantum, e is electron charge and h is the Planck's constant.

Experimental Methods

Sample and tip preparation: The details of the fabrication process of the MEMS devices were provided in ref.⁵. Gold tips were prepared by electrochemical etching of gold wires with a diameter of 0.25 mm with 99.99+% purity (GoodFellow) in $CaCl_2$, using the procedure reported by Boyle et al.⁶. Typical tip radius obtained with this etching procedure are 50 to 100 nm. Cleaning the gold surface on the MEMS devices is performed by a combination of O₂ plasma and ion milling. Before depositing the molecules, the samples are cleaned by O₂ plasma (400W for 5 min) to remove resist residues and other hydrocarbons coming from the lab environment. We then perform an Ar - ion milling step (beam current 150 mA with 30 cm as beam diameter for 20 s) to physically clean the top surface. After cleaning the MEMS, we then immerse it in the solution of the target molecules. In the case of OPE3, we obtained the molecules with acetyl-protected thiol groups, from Sigma Aldrich and an additional purification step (purity $\geq 99\%$) was then performed. For the deposition, Sample 1 was immersed in a solution of dichloromethane (DCM) with concentration $c = 1\text{mM}$ for 2 min. Two equivalents of tetrabutylammonium hydroxide (i.e., one TBAH molecule per acetyl group) were added to the solution to deprotect the thiol groups and improve the formation of the S-Au bond. A similar procedure was employed for Sample 2, but with $c = 0.25\text{mM}$ for 30 min. In both cases, the MEMS samples were then rinsed in a mixture of clean DCM and ethanol and carefully dried

under N₂ flow. In the case of ODT, we obtained the molecules from Sigma Aldrich (purity $\geq 97\%$) and used ethanol as a solvent. Sample 1 was immersed in a solution with $c = 1.2$ mM for 30 s, then rinsed twice in clean ethanol and dried with N₂. Similarly, for Sample 2 we used $c = 0.3$ mM and 30s.

Uncertainty calculation of experimental data: The uncertainty reported for the thermal conductance of the molecular junctions are composed of 2 main contributions: the RMS error of the 2D distribution ϵ_d and the error obtained by subtracting the linear fits of the thermal background. In the first case, we calculate the RMS error of the datapoints in the 2D histogram from the calculated mean at $x = 0.1$ nm and divide it by the square root of the number of traces used to build the histogram. Note that as the width of the histogram is homogeneous around the breaking point ($x = 0$), the RMS error does not change if calculated at another displacement value (e.g. $x = -0.1$ nm). To evaluate the error in extracting the step height from the linear fits, we consider the RMS error of the fit with respect to the mean of the 2D histogram within the fit range before and after the breaking point, respectively ϵ_b and ϵ_a . Finally, the total uncertainty is given by $\epsilon_{tot} = \sqrt{\epsilon_d^2 + \epsilon_b^2 + \epsilon_a^2}$. For instance, for the OPE3 dataset shown in Figure 2, we obtain in the fit range: $\epsilon_d = 5$ pW/K, $\epsilon_b = 2.8$ pW/K (fit range $-0.4 < x < -0.02$) and $\epsilon_a = 2.8$ pW/K ($0.02 < x < 0.4$) corresponding to $\epsilon_{tot} = 6.4$ pW/K. The fit range is always taken symmetric with respect to the breaking point. Variations in the step height that can result from the noise in the mean are included in the uncertainty range calculated with this method. To further check the robustness of the data analysis method, we verify that mean and median of the 2D histograms give the same result within 10%. The median is less sensitive to the occurrence of outliers in the histogram and therefore a useful cross-check of the quality of the data.

Data analysis procedure: In order to extract the thermal conductance of the molecular junction, we used 2D histograms collecting hundreds of thermal conductance versus displacement traces, showing molecular plateaus in the corresponding electrical conductance signal. Even though the contribution of a single molecule to the thermal conductance (~ 20 pW/K) is on the same order of the rms noise of the measured signal (~ 25 pW/K to 50 pW/K with an integration time of 1 ms), by taking the mean of the 2D histogram we can average out the random fluctuations occurring during the measurement and extract the molecular signature. Thermal conductance of the molecule is extracted by taking the difference of the value of the measured thermal conductance immediately before and after breaking of the molecular junction.

The method therefore relies on the identification of the breaking point of a molecular junction in the electrical conductance trace, very similarly to what has been done previously for the measurement of breaking forces^{7,8}. We defined criteria to locate the breaking point of the molecular plateaus automatically that were applied to all the datasets. Specifically, we defined as region of interest the electrical conductance range where the molecular plateau is expected, which is $8 - 30 \cdot 10^{-5} G_0$ for OPE3 and $2 - 8 \cdot 10^{-5} G_0$ for ODT. Molecular plateaus should be at least 50 ms long (~ 50 to 100 pm at usual perpendicular opening speeds of 1 pm/ms), to avoid artefacts of the thermal low-pass filtering. Finally, traces showing a ratio in electrical conductance before and after the breaking point of the molecular junction lower than 3 are

excluded. This condition serves to exclude traces from the analysis which carry significant uncertainty on the configuration of the molecular junction.

The only selection condition that we apply on the thermal signal is based on the thermal background slope. Datasets with non-linear or strongly varying background slopes over time indicate unstable experimental conditions and were not utilized in this work. In fact, the scatter in the mean and corresponding fitting uncertainty would be too large to be considered a significant result. Few examples of selected and not selected traces are reported in Fig. S5 and Fig. S6 in the SM for ODT and OPE3, respectively.

Fig. S1. Experimental results obtained for OPE3-dithiol as shown in Figure 4 of the main paper. a) The histograms are built from 223 traces measured at a fixed voltage $V = 50$ mV, angle = 40° and perpendicular opening speed $v = 2$ nm/s (Sample 1). Note that even though the electrical conductance peak in the 1D histogram (blue) is slightly shifted to higher values, the orange histogram, corresponding to the breaking configuration, agrees well with the other reported datasets, with a peak around $1 \cdot 10^{-4} G_0$. b) The histograms are built from 310 traces measured at 40 mV, angle = 30° , $v = 1$ nm/s (Sample 2). The shorter plateau length visible in the 2D histogram agrees well with previous reports⁹ and it may indicate a different pulling mechanism with respect to a). Note that the displacement scale along the pulling direction may carry significant uncertainty because of surface roughness.

Fig. S2. Experimental results obtained for OPE3-dithiol as shown in Figure 4 of the main paper. All the histograms were measured at $V = 90$ mV: a) Sample 1, 1130 traces, Angle = 23° , $v = 0.5$ nm/s. b) Sample 2, 301 traces, Angle = 25° , $v = 0.5$ nm/s. c) Sample 1, 254 traces, Angle = 27° , $v = 1$ nm/s. d) Sample 1, 316 traces, Angle = 23° , $v = 2$ nm/s.

Fig. S3. Thermal conductance of a single gold atom. The histogram is built with 991 traces, showing plateaus that are at least 20 ms long (calculated from the speed of 3 nm/s of this trace), applying the same data analysis method used for the molecular junctions in the electrical conductance range $0.8 G_0 < G < 1.2 G_0$.

Fig. S4. Electrical (a) and thermal (b) conductance histograms obtained for ODT by using closing curves. The histograms were built with 440 traces and measured at $V = 90$ mV with an angle = 23° with respect to the MEMS surface. In this case, $x = 0$ nm corresponds to the formation of the molecular junction.

Fig. S5. Examples of single opening traces for ODT. a-b) Selected traces used to build the histograms reported in Figure 3 of the main paper. c-d) Discarded traces, because not showing clear molecular plateaus (c) or clear breaking of the molecular junction (d).

Fig. S6. Examples of single opening traces for OPE3. a-b) Selected traces used to build the histograms reported in Figure 2 of the main paper. c-d) Discarded traces, because not showing clear breaking of the molecular junction.

Fig. S7. Molecular structure of (a) OPE3 and (b) ODT between gold electrodes.

Table S1. Spectral adjustment (DFT+ Σ) relative energies in the unit of eV. $-IP-E_H$ ($-EA-E_L$) are calculated from the gas-phase molecules. Z is energy shifts due to image charges screened by metal electrodes in the molecular junctions. Σ_o and Σ_u are the total corrections to Kohn-Sham DFT energy levels.

	-IP-E _H	-EA-E _L	Z	Σ _o =-IP-E _H +Z	Σ _u =-EA-E _L -Z
OPE3	-1.17	1.63	0.42	-0.75	1.23
ODT	-1.81	1.47	0.56	-1.25	0.91

Stiffness considerations:

Modelling the mechanical stiffness of the MEMS is quite challenging, as it depends on many parameters that are not easily accessible, like the residual stress in the layers after fabrication, the torsional and flexural bending modes, the thermal stress induced during operation because of the thermal expansion of the SiN_x and metallic layers. However, to give an estimate of the out-of-plane stiffness, we can use linear elastic continuum theory expressions for double-clamped beams under stress

$$k_{\perp} = 16 \frac{Ewt^3}{L^3} + \frac{24\sigma wt}{5L}$$

where σ represents the tensile uniaxial stress along the silicon nitride beams. By modelling the MEMS as two SiN_x beams of length $L = 600 \mu\text{m}$ (equal to the length of the two beams plus the central platform), thickness $t = 150 \text{ nm}$, width $w = 4 \mu\text{m}$, Young's modulus $E = 260 \text{ GPa}$ and tensile stress $\sim 75 \text{ MPa}$, we obtain a stiffness of $\sim 0.7 \text{ N/m}$, strongly dominated by the stress term.

However, by performing the first experiments, we found out that by simply moving the STM tip at an angle with respect to the MEMS surface, we can take advantage of the larger in-plane stiffness and achieve a controlled breaking process, without changing the fabrication process. In particular, if the beams are designed at an angle with respect to the axis of the MEMS, we can reduce the torsional degrees of freedom and exploit the uniaxial stiffness of the beams

$$k_{\parallel} = E \frac{wt}{L} \sin(\beta)$$

with values of about 135 N/m for a single beam. In fact, if the applied force is not perpendicular to the beam axis, we have to consider the contribution of the bending and of the elongation along the axis. We would like to point out that the estimations given here carry uncertainties since we consider only a very simplified model of the MEMS structure. Nevertheless, they serve to explain the empirical finding of a very different in-plane and out-of-plane stiffness resulting, for example, in different spring-loading distances in the two directions.

The angle is measured with respect to the surface normal and was empirically chosen to maximise the time the break-junction stays in certain plateaus. We note that the surface roughness of the sensors is significant (nanometers on a micron scale) and that the nominal angle is expected smaller than the actual angle between separating surfaces on a local scale. Surface with low roughness on the order of 0.1 nm on a micron scale could not be used for the experiments. We note, that we were able to increase the controllability of the break-junction measurements (i.e. with apparently stiff enough sensors) using gold surfaces with roughness. The experimental procedure includes finding approximately the smallest angle possible to detach the tip from the surface. We therefore envision that locally at the junction the facing surfaces are more perpendicular than the few 10s of degrees of angle chosen. Therefore, the effective stiffness can be significantly higher than the low stiffness in the normal direction to the MEMS sensor plane.

Estimation of the uncertainty related to a backlash

As discussed in the main manuscript, the effect of backlash could induce an artificial, positive contribution on the extracted molecular conductance, which we call G_{err} . This is related to the backlash Δz and the slope of the background by:

$$G_{\text{err}} = \Delta z \times dG/dz$$

The backlash Δz , in turn, can be estimated from the ratio of breaking force F_{break} and effective stiffness k of the sensor.

In the following, we collect different, and independent evidence that the expected error G_{err} is smaller than the uncertainty extracted from the procedure described in the manuscript.

In the following estimates, we use a value of 1 nN, which is a typical value used in several independent studies. We argue in the main text, that the force acting during breaking of the molecular junction may be lowered with respect to several literature studies. However, while a final conclusion on the break force is not available, we use this value as a conservative estimate. We note, that the force to break a Au-Au contact and an Au-thiol contact is about the same.

1) Snap-in versus snap-out experiments

The fact that the data extracted for opening and closing traces agree is an indication for the lack of significant snap-in or snap-out effects. The measured difference of the approach and retraction experiments is

$$G_{\text{diff}} = 2 \pm 9 \text{ pW/K}$$

This low value is in agreement with the notion of a relatively steep potential for the Au-Au binding force during breaking, only if we have a sufficiently large stiffness of the sensor. Using a Lennard Jones potential fitting the Au-Au bond and a break force of 1 nN, we conclude that we have a minimum of 20 N/m, and that ~ 21 N/m are sufficient to exclude any snap-in or snap-out process, i.e. having no backlash at all. We note finally, that additional forces (such as van der Waals) will lead to a weakening of the force gradients involved and therefore relax the requirement on sensor stiffness even further.

2) Ability to measure quantization steps in Au-Au contacts

The ability of our sensor system to measure reliably the conductance quantization of Au-Au atomic contacts^{5,10} is a further strong indication that our effective stiffness is much larger than 0.7 N/m. The argument is as follows.

Literature describes the forces needed to break atomic contacts in gold is about 1 nN per conductance quantum. A very common transition (also found predominantly in our data) is the transition from 3 G_0 to 1 G_0 in a single trace. To break the 3 G_0 contact a 3 nN force is necessary. If the force was not sufficiently relaxed (through unloading of the spring) then the 3 nN, being much larger than the 1 nN breaking force of a 1 G_0 contact, would break the 1 G_0 contact immediately. Measurements using stiff systems have shown an average plateau length of the 1 G_0 plateau at room temperature of 43 pm¹¹. To be able to have significant counts on a 1 G_0 plateau, we therefore require:

$$k > (3 \text{ nN} - 1 \text{ nN}) / 0.043 \text{ nm} = 47 \text{ N/m}$$

According to the above argument, this should suffice to suppress any sensor backlash.

We note, even if the argument using the snap-in and snap-out using the Lennard-Jones potential would not apply, we can assume that for a 1 nN break force, would yield a backlash of $43 \text{ pm} / 2 = 22 \text{ pm}$ based on literature data. Applying a background slope of 0.5 nW/K/nm as in some of our experiments, we find

$$G_{\text{error}} < 22 \text{ pm} \times 0.5 \text{ nW/K/nm} = 11 \text{ pW/K.}$$

3) The observed lack of dependence on value of background slope

Next we consider our measurement results of Fig. 4 of the manuscript. The slope through the conductance data vs background slope is small, such that we find a variation of 5 pW and 7 pW for OPE3 and ODT, respectively. This we take as estimates of the systematic error

$$G_{\text{error}} < 6 \text{ pW/K}$$

Applying the simple equation again, we conclude that the backlash distance Δz would have been less than 3 pm .

4) Summary on backlash uncertainty

In summary, these three arguments give us:

Argument	max G_{err}	max backlash Δz	min k
Snap-in vs out	3 pW/K	2 pm	20 N/m
Au conductance steps	$(11 \text{ pW/K})^*$	22 pm	46 N/m
background slope	6 pW/K	3 pm	

* ignoring finite force gradient of Au-Au bond and only for illustration. Otherwise the error would be 0 pW/K .

The uncertainty we quote due to possible back-lash is estimated to be below the uncertainty of the measurement in main text.

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